

Esr Spectral Studies on some Perovskite Catalysts containing Titanium and Vanadium

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Manuscript received 19 July 1985, revised 2 September 1986, accepted 30 October 1986

Electron spin resonance spectral studies have been carried out on vanadium-incorporated SrTiO₃ and the spectra have been interpreted on the basis of valence state and dispersion of vanadium ions in the lattice. A comparison with the spectra of mixed oxides of titanium and vanadium has also been made.

THE V₂O₅-TiO₂ mixed oxides have been established as versatile, selective and durable catalysts for the oxidation of orthoxylene to phthalic anhydride^{1,2}. Besides being a structural promoter, TiO₂ also seems to stabilise the oxidation state of vanadium³. Yabrov *et al.*⁴ and Cole *et al.*⁵ independently reported that on heating a mixture of anatase and V₂O₅ to around 750°, anatase becomes rutile, V₂O₅ is reduced to V₂O₄, and V^{IV} enters the rutile lattice. Esr studies on the above mixed oxide system have also been carried out^{6,7}. It was therefore thought interesting to study the effect of titanium on the valence state of vanadium when both the ions are incorporated in the B sites of a perovskite structure. The present work is an attempt to study the valence state of vanadium in a titanate perovskite vis-a-vis V₂O₅, V₂O₄ and V₂O₅-TiO₂ mixed oxide systems through esr studies.

Experimental

V₂O₅-TiO₂ mixed oxides were prepared⁸. Calcination at 450° gave yellow samples and at 800° gave black samples. X-Ray diffraction revealed anatase phase in the low temperature preparation (AVY), and rutile in the high temperature preparation (RVB). V-substituted titanate perovskites (STV) were prepared by impregnating TiO₂ with an aqueous solution of Sr(NO₃)₂ and NH₄VO₃, and drying followed by calcination at 850° for 48 h,

with intermittent grinding. X-Ray diffraction revealed only a perovskite phase. STV materials are perovskites, containing vanadium and titanium in the B sites of SrTiO₃. The figures at the end of the symbols denote the atomic per cent of vanadium in the samples. For instance, STV-20 denotes that the concentration of vanadium in the sample is 20 atomic per cent.

Esr spectra of the catalysts were recorded in a Varian E-112 spectrometer with a magnetic field of around 3200 G, microwave frequency of 9.70 GHz and microwave power of 10 mW. The small pip on each trace corresponds to a *g* value of 2.0028 (marker used was TCNE). Esr parameters of the samples are given in Table 1. For spectra possessing axial symmetry the two *g* values as well as the two *A* values were calculated following the method of Hecht and Johnstone⁹. For singlet spectra the *g* value was calculated from the distance between the signal for the sample and that for TCNE. The relative intensities of the different signals were determined using a computer programme following the procedure of Ayscough⁹.

Results and Discussion

In the esr signals of transition metal ions which have a positive spin-orbit coupling constant, *g* is usually less than the free-spin value (2.002). Both V^{IV} and Ti^{III} have positive spin-orbit coupling constants. Yet one of the *g* components in most

TABLE 1—ESR PARAMETERS OF PEROVSKITE CATALYSTS CONTAINING TITANIUM AND VANADIUM

Sample	Temp. K	<i>g</i> Factor			Hfs (cm ⁻¹)		Relative intensity
		<i>g</i> _{II}	<i>g</i> _I	<i>g</i> _{av}	<i>A</i> _{II}	<i>A</i> _I	
AVY-10	293	2.017	1.963	1.981	No Hfs		14.2
RVB-10	293	—	—	1.963	No Hfs		24.1
STV-10	293	2.004	1.995	1.998	70.34	31.02	1.0
STV-20	293	1.993	1.955	1.968	159.6	26.77	3.17
STV-25	293	2.019	1.926	1.957	166.5	49.58	3.13
STV-29	293	1.957	2.022	2.000	163.2	38.05	2.17
V ₂ O ₅	293	—	—	1.963	No Hfs		30.0
V ₂ O ₄	293	—	—	1.972	No Hfs		44.4

of the anisotropic signals in this work has a value nearer to the free-spin value and at times greater than the free-spin value. This can be ascribed to the presence of F-centres as well as adsorbed ionic oxygen species such as O^- , O_2^- , which have anisotropic g values in the range 2.001–2.08 (Refs. 10 and 11).

AVY-10 has a spectrum with a g the same as the g value of V_2O_5 . This has been attributed by earlier workers to the presence of V^{IV} ions¹². Such an explanation is also applicable here because AVY-10 is only a mixed oxide of TiO_2 and V_2O_5 . But the intriguing aspect of the spectrum is its highly anisotropic nature. It is well known that anisotropy of the g factor depends on the spin-orbit coupling and splitting of the energy levels of the paramagnetic ions caused by crystalline fields surrounding it¹³. The environment of the paramagnetic ion must therefore be non-uniform.

The spectra of RVB-10 is a singlet (free from hfs). The intensity of RVB-10 is much higher than that of AVY-10. This is indicative of the fact that V^{IV} ions in AVY-10 arise only from V_2O_5 while in RVB-10 they arise from the solid solution of VO_2 and TiO_2 , as well as from V_2O_5 .

The A tensor of STV-10 appears to be so anisotropic that the spectrum appears virtually non-resolvable. Though the pattern is difficult to resolve, two aspects appear prominent: the intensities of the lines are small and line broadening is not much. This suggests that the concentration of V^{IV} ions is small and some of these ions are present as clusters¹⁴. STV-20 and STV-25 present a very nearly identical spectrum with sharp signals in contrast to the broad signals of V_2O_5 and V_2O_4 . This points to the fact that V^{IV} of the heterocation VO^{II} is present in very small number in the STV materials compared to their amounts in the vanadium oxides. This also explains the absence of spin-spin broadening in the spectra of STV series.

The intensities of the signals decrease in the sequence: STV-20 > STV-25 > STV-29. A decrease in intensity with increasing vanadium content may be the result of a progressively more uniform distribution of vanadium ions in the perovskite lattice. An equally possible reason is the increase in covalence of the V–O bond¹⁵. The larger hfs observed for STV-25 compared to that for STV-20 and STV-29 is a reflection of the difference in covalent character of the V–O bond in the perovskites. This is in line with the change in the hfs observed by Muller¹⁶ on doping $SrTiO_3$ with Cr^{III} and Mn^{IV} . Though the signal originates only from V^{IV} and not from V^V , which is diamagnetic, hfs pertains to all V nuclei with a nuclear spin of $7/2$. Information regarding all the V–O bonds in the perovskite is thus obtained from hfs irrespective of the oxidation state of vanadium in the lattice.

The narrowness of the central line, only 5 G, for STV-20 proves that the environment of the V ions is cubic to a high degree. The g anisotropy of the STV-29 spectrum arises from the heterogeneity of the lattice points, viz. V ions occupying some of the titanium positions. On the other hand, the anisotropy of STV-20 and STV-25 stems from the tetragonality of the lattice as well as from the partial replacement of Ti and V ions. The difference in line width between the signals of STV-29 on the one hand, and of STV-20 and STV-25 on the other, can be accounted for partially by exchange narrowing. As already mentioned some of the g components of the STV materials are very nearly equal to the free-spin value. A g value larger than the free-spin value may mean the occurrence of one or more of the following phenomena: (i) F-centres, (ii) ionosorbed oxygen species, (iii) highly covalent or free-radical like characteristics of the vanadium domains, and (iv) coupling of the unpaired electron with filled rather than with partially filled orbitals. The last feature would mean that most of the Ti and V ions in this perovskite are in their highest oxidation states.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. N. K. Chengappa, Principal, Prof. G. Kannaian, Professor of Physics, and Dr. R. Natesan, Professor of Chemistry, Government College of Technology, Coimbatore, for permitting to submit this paper.

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